

Anionic Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cobalt(II) and Copper(II)

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Manuscript received 13 December 1982, revised 6 June 1986, accepted 18 June 1986

Anionic mixed ligand complexes of the compositions $[LH]_2[MCl_4L'_2]$, where LH = 2,6-lutidinium cation, L' = pyridine, piperidine for Co^{2+} and quinaldine, γ - and β -picoline for Cu^{2+} ; $[LH]_2[MCl_4L-L]$, where L-L = 1,10-phenanthroline, 2,2'-bipyridyl for Co^{2+} and 1,10-phenanthroline, *o*-phenylenediamine for Cu^{2+} ; $[LH][CoCl_4\gamma\text{-picoline}]$, have been isolated. Analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, ir and electronic spectral data suggest distorted octahedral geometry for all the Co^{2+} complexes except the γ -picoline complex for which a tetrahedral stereochemistry is indicated.

SEVERAL anionic tetra-halo and tetra-pseudohalo complexes of divalent metal ions containing nitrogen and sulphur donor ligands have been reported by various workers¹⁻⁶. A number of tetra-, penta- and hexa-coordinated anionic mixed ligand complexes of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Cd^{2+} ions have been reported⁷⁻¹¹. Since the nature of cation can influence the coordination number of the central metal ion in an anionic complex, it was of interest to prepare mixed ligand anionic complexes containing a bulkier cation with uni- and multi-dentate nitrogen donor ligands.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Bis(2,6-lutidinium)tetrachlorocobaltate(II)/cuprate(II): Simple complexes of the type ML_2Cl_2 , where $M = Co^{2+}$ and Cu^{2+} ; $L = 2,6$ -lutidine, were prepared by reacting ethanolic solution of metal chlorides with heterocyclic amine separately in 1 : 2 stoichiometric proportions. Then pure and dry chlorine gas was passed slowly to ethanolic suspension of the above simple complexes till a clear solution was obtained. The reaction was exothermic and the solution was allowed to stand for 1-2 h. The crystals of $[LH]_2[MCl_4]$ separated out on cooling, were filtered, washed with a minimum volume of ethanol and dried in vacuum.

Mixed ligand complexes: Ethanolic solution of $[LH]_2[MCl_4]$, where $M = Co^{2+}$ or Cu^{2+} , was reacted with nitrogen donor mono- and bi-dentate ligands (1 : 2 ratio) and refluxed for 1-2 h on a water-bath. Crystalline mixed ligand complexes separated out on cooling, were filtered, washed with a minimum volume of ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuum.

Metal and chloride contents of the complexes were estimated by complexometric EDTA titration

method¹². Conductance was measured in $10^{-3}M$ acetone solution using Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made by Gouy method. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer 221 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra of $10^{-3}M$ solution of the complexes in chloroform were recorded on a Hilger-Watt UVISPECK spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of elemental analysis and conductance data (Table 1), the compositions of the complexes have been found to be $[LH]_2[CoCl_4(py)_2]$, $[LH]_2[CoCl_4(1,10\text{-phen})]$, $[LH]_2[CoCl_4(dipy)]$, $[LH][CoCl_4(\gamma\text{-pic})]$, $[LH]_2[CoCl_4(\gamma\text{-pic})_2]$ or $(\beta\text{-pic})_2$ or $(quin)_2$, $[LH]_2[CuCl_4(1,10\text{-phen or } o\text{-phen})]$.

Magnetic moment values of Co^{2+} complexes (~ 5.0 B.M.) were in conformity with octahedral configuration except the γ -picoline complex for which μ_{eff} was 4.4 B.M. suggesting a tetrahedral stereochemistry of the metal ion. The magnetic moment value of the Cu^{2+} complexes were in the range 1.74-1.78 B.M. indicating the presence of one unpaired electron. The conductance value (Λ_M) of γ -picoline- Co^{2+} complex is $120 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ indicating 1 : 1 electrolytic nature whereas the values for all other complexes lie in the range 220-240 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ indicating 2 : 1 electrolytic nature.

The occurrence¹³ of ν_{N-H} and δ_{N-H} bands in the ir spectra of the complexes at ~ 3300 and $\sim 1590 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively, indicates the presence of lutidinium cation. The pyridine and the picoline adducts show bands in the region $1600-1430 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $\nu_{C=C}$ and ν_{C-N} , and a change of $\sim 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the mixed ligand complexes indicates the bonding of these heterocyclic amines to the metal ions¹⁴. The absorption bands at 840 and 760 cm^{-1} due to C-H out-of-plane vibration, and the shifting of ring stretching by $\sim 10-20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ to higher frequencies

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	M p °C	Analysis % · Found/(Calcd)		Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B M
			metal	Chloride		
[LH] ₂ [CoCl ₄ (py) ₂]	Pink	210	10.60 (10.25)	24.25 (24.09)	220.0	5.0
[LH] ₂ [CoCl ₄ (pip) ₂]	Pink	220	9.89 (10.04)	24.07 (24.19)	230.0	5.1
[LH] ₂ [CoCl ₄ (1,10-phen)]	Pink	200	9.72 (9.90)	23.58 (23.86)	240.0	4.9
[LH] ₂ [CoCl ₄ (2,2'-bipy)]	Brown	250	8.29 (8.40)	20.13 (20.25)	220.0	5.0
[LH][CoCl ₄ (γ -pic)]	Blue	140	15.95 (16.12)	28.97 (29.11)	120.0	4.4
[LH] ₂ [CuCl ₄ (γ -pic) ₂]	Light blue	195	9.94 (10.12)	22.48 (22.62)	235.0	1.75
[LH] ₂ [CuCl ₄ (β -pic) ₂]	Blue	78	10.08 (10.12)	22.57 (22.62)	220.0	1.78
[LH] ₂ [CuCl ₄ (quin) ₂]	Black	150	9.28 (9.37)	20.72 (20.90)	230.0	1.74
[LH] ₂ [CuCl ₄ (<i>o</i> -phend)]	Black	215	10.34 (10.42)	23.17 (23.29)	235.0	1.75
[LH] ₂ [CuCl ₄ (1,10-phen)]	Green	205	10.47 (10.59)	23.52 (23.65)	220.0	1.77

LH = 2,6-Lutidinium cation; py = pyridine; pip = piperidine; γ -pic = γ -picoline; β -pic = β -picoline; quin = quinoline; *o*-phend = *o*-phenylenediamine; 2,2'-bipy = 2,2'-bipyridine; 1,10-phen = 1,10-phenanthroline.

in the mixed ligand complexes, indicates the bonding of 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline to the metal ions^{1,5,16}. Evidence for the coordination of the nitrogen donor ligand has been further substantiated by the occurrence of band at $\sim 510 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to ν_{M-N} .

All the Co²⁺ complexes except [LH][CoCl₄(γ -pic)] show two bands at 9 600 and 21 000 cm^{-1} assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)(\nu_1)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(\nu_2)$ transitions, respectively, and a very weak band at $\sim 18 000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(\nu_3)$ transition. The latter complex, however, shows two bands at 8 500 and 15 000 cm^{-1} attributable to ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ and ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(F)$ transitions, respectively. The band positions and assignments thereof in conjugation with the magnetic moment values discussed, suggest a tetrahedral geometry for [LH][CoCl₄(γ -pic)] and octahedral geometry for all other Co²⁺ complexes.

Copper(II) complexes show one band in the region 13 500–16 000 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to the transition ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$, characteristic of the distorted octahedral configuration¹⁷.

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